

A HISTORICAL OVERVIEW OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIA AND COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: The historical development of media and communication is a complex and multifaceted process reflecting changes in socio-economic, political and technological conditions. This development began with ancient forms of information transmission, such as oral storytelling and handwritten documents. The invention of the printing press by Johannes Gutenberg in the mid-15th century was a revolutionary step that ushered in the era of mass production of books and newspapers, greatly expanding access to information. In the 19th century, the telegraph and telephone made a qualitative leap in the speed and scope of communication, allowing messages to be transmitted over long distances in a matter of minutes.

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The historical development of media and communication is a complex and multifaceted process reflecting changes in socio-economic, political and technological conditions. This development began with ancient forms of information transmission, such as oral storytelling and handwritten documents. The invention of the printing press by Johannes Gutenberg in the mid-15th century was a revolutionary step that ushered in the era of mass production of books and newspapers, greatly expanding access to information. In the 19th century, the telegraph and telephone made a qualitative leap in the speed and scope of communication, allowing messages to be transmitted over long distances in a matter of minutes. The 20th century was marked by the advent of radio broadcasting and television, which radically changed the way information was disseminated, making it more rapid and visually rich. At the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, digital technology and the Internet created another revolution, creating a global network for instant information sharing and communication, which led to the emergence of new forms of media, such as social networks and blogs. Modern media and communication are characterized by a high degree of interactivity and accessibility, changing not only the methods of information transmission, but also the very nature of social interaction.

It should be noted that Julius Caesar was the first ruler of his time to realize that for the normal development of society, it is necessary to inform it about certain

information about state life, characterized by the importance of both the state and the society itself.

Besides, it should be mentioned that classical handwritten newspapers were used. Thus, in ancient Rome began to use special, so-called “information” walls, which later received the notion of “albumus”.

For a long time, the collection and processing of information was carried out without the main socializing process - dissemination of information. This was due to the idea that by acquiring this or that important information, the state gets a certain advantage, “power”, and providing the population with relevant information implies their “strengthening”, which was not always expedient for the state.

The basic model of the communicative process was formulated long ago by ancient scholars. Thus, Aristotle noted that any communication involves at least three elements: the speaker, the message he produces, and the person to whom the message is intended. By “speaker” Aristotle seems to have understood not only oral speakers, but also people who write, since in his time the handwriting culture was already well developed and he himself is known to have published some of his works in written form. At the same time, comparing his model of social communication with the modern models of Shannon and Lasswell, we notice that it does not mention at all the technical means of communication between senders and receivers of information, i.e. the means of recording, storing, replicating, transmitting and receiving it. This is quite explainable by the level of socio-cultural and technological development of the ancient society. Hence, we can conclude that the whole further history of social communication development consisted in the consistent development and perfection of technical means, which in Aristotle's time either did not exist at all or were in an embryonic state.

This was the conclusion reached by the famous Canadian sociologist and art historian M. McLuhan (1911-1980), author of the famous concept of modern society, which he envisioned as an “electronic society” and a “global village”.

The periodization of world history proposed by M. McLuhan has been controversial. McLuhan's periodization of world history has received a mixed assessment of the scientific community, which was facilitated in no small measure by the general methodological principle used in his works. As is well known, McLuhan focused on the cultural-psychological and emotional-aesthetic aspects of social communication rather than on the technical side of the matter, which is traditional for the Western scientific approach. In this we see both the main advantage of his works (shifting the emphasis from the technical to the humanitarian side of the case) and a certain disadvantage (excessive psychologism). In addition, the parallel drawn by McLuhan between “agrarian - industrial - post-industrial” society and “oral - printed - electronic” forms of mass communication is not quite correct, since one is fundamentally unrelated to the other. In particular, printing is only a form of written communication, which emerged long before the development of industry. Printing does not bring anything new, except facilitating (and

cheapening) the replication of written documents. While it is true that printing puts the replication of written documents on an industrialized basis, a much more important step in the development of the means of communication is the invention of writing itself.

Before we proceed to the analysis of the main stages of development of social communication media, it is necessary to define the following content varieties.

First, social communication can be interpersonal or mass communication. In personal communication, the senders and receivers of messages are individuals - one or more people. Examples of this form of communication can be an ordinary conversation between two or more people or an ordinary telephone conversation. Mass communication, on the other hand, assumes that the recipient or sender of messages is necessarily a large number of people (masses). Examples of such forms of communication can be rallies, watching movies, listening to radio programs, etc. It is not necessarily the case that masses of people are only recipients of information, as they can also be active generators of information, for example, during rallies, demonstrations, marches, etc. While the specificity and “articulateness” of information received from large masses of people during such events is of course much less than in the case of speeches by individuals, large masses of people can nevertheless be seen as generators and senders of information messages. Such forms of communication should be considered as forms of mass communication.

Second, all forms of social communication can be divided into private communication and official communication. This division is very rarely made in the literature on social communication, but it is important. Private communication includes all forms of communication carried out in public life between private individuals, such as ordinary conversations, telephone conversations, social networking, etc. If one of the parties of communication - the sender or the receiver of messages, is an official person, then such forms of communication are referred to official. It is easy to see that it is official communication that plays the most important role in public life. Official communications, publication of laws, orders and instructions of the official authorities, diplomatic correspondence, exchange of information between officials of different states in the international arena, etc., all have a much greater impact on society than the current exchange of information between private individuals. Of no less importance is the information sent to official authorities or institutions by the masses themselves. And it can be sent both spontaneously (during mass events: rallies, marches, in the form of mass written appeals of citizens, etc.) and in the form of mass surveys conducted by official and unofficial institutions (sociological services).

Finally, thirdly, it is necessary to distinguish between one-way communication and two-way communication, or communication with feedback. In the first case, only one of the parties is active, i.e., can transmit information messages, and the second can only receive information, but cannot transmit its message to the sender. Such, for example, is the communication during watching

TV programs and movies, listening to radio programs, reading books and newspapers, etc. In the course of communication with feedback, the recipients of messages can themselves transmit their messages to the sender, as it happens, for example, during telephone conversations, participation in rallies, discussion of any issues in social networks, etc. As a matter of fact, only the second type of communication fully corresponds to the notion of communication, and its first type should be called simply the transfer of information. It is not by chance that traditional means of mass communication - press, radio, television - are called mass media (informing), as they did not initially (in full) realize feedback with their readers, listeners, viewers, although some feedback, for example, through mail, was undoubtedly realized with these media. At the current stage of development of these media, the state of affairs has changed significantly. But this has happened mainly due to the development of electronic technical means of transmitting and presenting information. Данное развитие СМИ, по-нашему мнению, осуществлялось следующим образом.

This development of the mass media, in our opinion, was carried out in the following way.

Its initial stage, as McLuhan pointed out, was a society in which the oral form of communication prevailed. No technical means of communication at this stage yet existed, and all kinds and forms of communication were carried out in conditions of direct contact between people - at a distance of direct sight and hearing between them and only in real time. For mass communication its participants had to gather in one place - in a theater, on the square, stadium, etc. Private and official, one-way and two-way communication were carried out in this form.

However, already at this stage of development of social communication, the separation and isolation of its two main directions became clear: communication in space and communication in time. Different people with different abilities and different social institutions that emerged around them assumed the functions of supporting these two directions of social communication. Thus, for example, narrators, rhapsodes, boyans, philosophical and ordinary schools for children carried out the transmission of social information in time (from generation to generation), while all kinds of courier institutions transmitted it in space.

The “nouvelle vague” have not disappeared in our time, moreover, with the development of the Internet, their activity in the information field is experiencing, one could say, its second birth.

The next fundamental step in the development of technical means of communication and information storage was the invention of mechanical sound recording and reproduction devices: the phonograph and the gramophone, which made it possible to record and reproduce information messages directly from the voice, bypassing the technology of writing. Gramophone records could now be used (and on a mass scale) by completely illiterate people (who could not read or write).

Social communication thus began to return to a pre-written, oral era, which was emphasized with particular force in McLuhan's concept.

However, the emergence of these new means of recording and reproducing sounds did not lead to the emergence of new means of delivery. Mail was still used here. However, the technologies soon developed for recording and reproducing sounds and images by means of electrical and electromagnetic engineering made it possible to use these principles also to transmit recorded information over long distances by wire or over the airwaves. The telephone, teletype and radio raised the whole sphere of social communication to a qualitatively new level and made it possible to achieve even greater mass information coverage of the population. Another breakthrough in this respect was the invention of television.

At its initial stage there are only natural means, channels of communication and information transfer. Namely, sound and visual channels of information transmission and perception, language as an artificial means of its coding and decoding and man as a natural carrier and transmitter of information in space and its keeper in time.

At the second stage, the emergence of fundamentally new means of coding (writing), storage (parchment, papyrus, paper) and recording of information leads to the emergence of two more new channels of communication and information transmission - mail and library (in the broad sense as an institution for storing manuscripts, documents, etc.). The highest level of development at this stage is the invention of printing, which accelerates and facilitates the mass reproduction of handwritten texts.

At the third stage, the emergence of fundamentally new non-written means of recording and reading information, first mechanical (phonograph and gramophone) and then electrical, makes it possible to achieve mass transmission of information over considerable distances and at great speed (wires and ether make it almost instantaneous).

Finally, at the last, modern stage, with the emergence of the possibility of coding information not in analog but in digital form, a fundamentally new means of recording, storing, transmitting and reproducing information emerges - computer technology and the Internet. Combining both a means of communication and a means of storing and transmitting social information over time, the Internet is becoming a single universal channel of social communication, and more and more mass.

Thus, in our opinion, the entire history of the development of mass communication (and social communication in general) should be divided not into three, but into the four principal stages of its development described above. At the same time, the second main stage should be recognized not as the development of the means of printing (as it is presented in M. McLuhan's concept), but as the development of writing as a whole, within the framework of which printing plays the role of the highest level of its development (only in terms of ensuring the mass circulation of

written texts). As for the last stage in the development of means of social communication, it should be recognized not as the development of radio and television, on which M. McLuhan stopped, but as the development of computer technology and the Internet. The specific feature of this stage is the achievement of universality in the means of recording, storing, replicating, transmitting, reproducing information, both audio, visual and written.

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